

RESEARCH ARTICLE

THE IMPORTANCE OF NURSING SURVEILLANCE IN POST-ANESTHESIA CARE

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Abstract

Background: Post anesthesia nursing care aims to act in advance on clinical instability resulting from surgery/anesthesia through surveillance, which comprises 20-50% of its activities, and is a critical and vulnerable moment for the person being cared for and highly complex for those managing the care. **Objectives:** The aim was to understand the interaction between nursing surveillance in post-anesthesia and the provision of care to ensure the safety of the person being cared for. **Method and materials:** Qualitative design research based on Grounded Theory. In-depth interviews were conducted with nurses who provide care in post-anesthesia care units through theoretical sampling, document analysis, observation and memos. Data analysis was assisted by the MAXQDA 2022 program. **Results:** The central category - the concept of surveillance - and the subsidiary categories were inferred, assuming the theory constructed in a narrative order: surveillance in post-anesthesia nursing care, through the establishment of a therapeutic relationship, leads to the practice of caring for the person safely. **Conclusion:** Increasing our understanding of this phenomenon will lead to interventions with implications for practice: enhancing a safer care environment through the exploration of predictors, as well as the creation of a theoretical model of post-anesthesia nursing surveillance.

Keywords: Nursing Care; Perioperative Care; Post-Anesthesia Care; Nursing.

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INTRODUCTION

The postoperative period refers to the time between the completion of surgical intervention and the person's full postoperative recovery (1). As framed by Regulation No. 428/2018 - Regulation of Specific Competences of the Nurse Specialist in Medical-Surgical Nursing in the area of Nursing to the Person in Perioperative Situation, the postoperative phase begins when the person is admitted to the Post-Anesthesia Care Unit (PACU) and ends when it is determined that the person has recovered from the surgical/anesthetic process (2).

Although the practice of anesthesia was established over 150 years ago, and the need for adequate spaces for postoperative care was recognized early on, Post-Anesthesia Care Units (PACUs) only experienced significant growth in the last five decades. In the 1980s, the scarcity of units was associated with a high incidence of anesthesia complications in France, prompting the anesthesia-surgical community to collaborate intensively for the viability and implementation of these units (3). Therefore, it is recommended that every person undergoing anesthetic intervention (general anesthesia, neuroaxial anesthesia, or monitoring care) be admitted to the PACU for post-anesthetic care (3).

The need for the creation of highly differentiated post-anesthetic units goes back to Florence Nightingale and the surveillance of anesthetic effects, the conception of a room by Gordon in 1904 for the removal of ether as an anesthetic gas from the body surface, the use of drugs enhancing respiratory depression, and the performance of thoracic surgeries, to neurosurgical surveillance before transfer to the ward, the exponential growth

of surgeries in the context of conflict in World War II, and the need for more advanced postoperative care (3). In addition, the structuring of the functional requirements of PACUs, the development of invasive monitoring techniques, and assisted ventilation, and the valuation of the post-anesthetic nursing specialty with the creation of the American Society of Post Anesthesia Nurses – ASPAN (4), are significant.

Since their creation, PACUs have been crucial for post-anesthesia care in maintaining the clinical integrity of the person through intensive multidisciplinary monitoring, protocol-based care to reduce clinical risk, the objectification of admission and stay in the unit to act during the period of greatest clinical vulnerability, with improvements in surgical outcomes and a significant reduction in postoperative morbidity and mortality and associated costs (4, 5).

Nurses are decisive for a proficient and intentional response to clinical changes secondary to surgery/anesthesia and the management of care throughout the process, namely in promoting safety involving the implementation of actions and protocols aimed at preventing accidents and complications and adopting measures of comfort and well-being that aim to promote physical and emotional comfort and ensure the overall well-being of the involved person (4). The goals of post-anesthesia nursing care are to meet the needs of the person during their stay in the unit, to perform continuous and critical postoperative assessment, to anticipate and prevent anesthesia and surgical complications, to be prepared to act competently in emergency situations, to establish an effective connection between the operating room, the person/family, and the inpatient or home services to

ensure a smooth transition(3). It is also important to highlight that post-anesthesia nursing care occurs in a highly complex and challenging clinical context, due to the need for management and assistance activities, determining quick and appropriate decision-making in various scenarios (6).

Surveillance is a nursing intervention recognized as an important strategy in preventing clinical errors and adverse events (7). The definition of surveillance proposed by the Nursing Interventions Classification (NIC) is the intentional and continuous acquisition, interpretation, and synthesis of clinical data for decision-making, which, upon further analysis, promotes and maintains the safety of the cared-for person (8). Minimizing errors and adverse events depends on the accuracy and timely critical assessment of the person's clinical status, including the evaluation of avoidable and unpredictable risk (8).

Although surveillance has been identified as a fundamental nursing intervention for maintaining the safety of the cared-for person, there are few studies that have described the effectiveness of surveillance patterns or the effect of surveillance on clinical outcomes. Thus, the theoretical evidence base for guiding nurses in performing the intervention is unavailable. Based on the analysis of theoretical assumptions, the research question was defined: How does nursing surveillance in post-anesthesia nursing care affect the safety of the cared-for person? To achieve the research for the expressed problem, the following objective was outlined: to understand the interaction of nursing surveillance in post-anesthesia nursing care and the safety of the cared-for person.

Despite the primary mission of post-anesthesia

nursing care in the post-anesthesia recovery process, it remains a lesser-known context within nursing practice. Closely related to the clinical area of the operating room and yet isolated from it, many professionals and families lack contact with this care context (9).

The experience of care in a complex and highly differentiated clinical context is illustrated by a clinical practice in an uncertain and fluctuating environment (10). This period of critical care and great vulnerability for the cared person combines the risk of complications associated with surgery and anesthesia, with a complication incidence of 40%, minor complication signals at 22.1%, and considering that half of these events occur in the first hour of admission to the PACU (11, 12).

Nurses continuously employ the process of nursing surveillance, being an active and essential part of care, allowing for the maintenance of safety and the prevention of the deterioration of the clinical state of those they care for (13). The main characteristics of nursing surveillance include collecting, analyzing, and interpreting information (data) for decision-making in praxis (14). Thus, nurses have the potential to minimize inadequate outcomes, prevent adverse events, or deterioration of the clinical status of the cared person (13). This potential influence on outcomes makes the exploration of the phenomenon interesting, being a critical point in the component of care provided by the nurse and a complex and significant concept for the cared person.

Despite nursing surveillance being associated with better outcomes for the cared person and the organizational context, evidence related to the impact of the operative process in the post-anes-

thetic context is scarce. It was observed, therefore, that the phenomenon under study is little explored in the Portuguese and international panorama, and its investigation could represent a valid contribution to the development of disciplinary nursing knowledge.

MATERIAL/METHODS

A qualitative approach based on Grounded Theory was adopted. The core of the research developed around nurses involved in post-anesthesia care at a central hospital in the central region of Portugal, through theoretical sampling.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria of the Sample

The inclusion criteria for participants were nurses providing post-anesthesia care, who agreed to participate voluntarily in the study.

Data Collection and Procedure

To seek meanings attributed to human experience, individual in-depth interviews were conducted with nurses providing care in PACUs. For the confirmation of data interpretation, participant validation was carried out through periodic meetings, as well as the provision of produced documents (diagrams, descriptive narratives). This comparative analysis, from the diagrams to the description of the interpretation and from this to the diagrams, allowed the detection of inconsistencies, favoring investigative reflexivity about their own interpretation.

Research Instrument

The researcher sought the protagonism of the participant through the free expression of opinions, experiences, and emotions, recognizing the constructive-interpretive and intersubjective dimension of the process of scientific knowledge

production through in-depth interviews (15).

In an interactive dimension of knowledge production and the researcher's participation in the observed phenomenon, behavioral observation of post-anesthesia nursing care provision was affected, advocating a constant search for its coherence with reality. Semiotic codes, non-linguistic but meaning-carrying elements such as gestures, various objects, and olfactory codes, were given attention.

Documentary analysis of nursing clinical records (primary source) aimed to understand the interaction with the source and create ways to understand the phenomenon. The document, as a means of communication, elaborated with purpose and intention, is an important tool for understanding who produced it, for whom it was constructed, and the intentionality of its elaboration (16).

Ethical Considerations

In accordance with ethical and deontological principles, informed consents were obtained, and anonymity and confidentiality of data were ensured. The study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the hospital center where the study was conducted.

RESULTS

The data analysis was centered around coding. The coding process took place in three phases: open, axial, and selective coding (15). Open coding involved breaking down, analyzing, comparing, conceptualizing, and categorizing the data. Properties and dimensions of categories were discovered, and incidents or events were grouped into codes through incident-to-incident comparison. In this process of constant questioning and

comparison, the conceptualization of the phenomenon under study began, breaking it down into units of analysis and questioning about them. The sample was differentiated based on the questions and ideas that emerged during the analysis, not representing the characteristics of the participants, but relevant to the phenomenon under study, being intentionally directed by the data analysis process. Interviews were analyzed as

they were conducted, ending when theoretical saturation was reached, that is, when the categories found began to stabilize.

The next step involved grouping concepts into categories, establishing relationships of similarity between concepts (figure 1). The naming of the category emerged from the meanings conveyed by the literature and the theoretical sensitivity of the researcher.

Fig.1 - Grouping central concepts into categories.

Codes were classified into categories that are representative of the phenomenon and categorized into: first-order codes, directly associated with quotes; and abstract or theoretical codes, linked to other codes, without necessarily being connected to any quote (15).

Axial coding examined the relationships between categories and subcategories. Defining the properties and characteristics of the categories allowed for the hierarchization of their conceptual structure and the identification of profiles (figure 2).

Fig. 2 - Axial coding: relationships between categories and subcategories.

Selective coding refined the entire process by identifying the core category of the theory, with which all others are related. To operationalize the coding, the process of labeling the created codes began and ended with the integration of the theory around the core category, the one that represents the phenomenon (figures 3 and 4). As interviews were read, codes were created and names assigned to significant quotes, objects, and events.

The codes were commented on, highlighting the characteristics of their representative idea's objective, as well as the criteria for linkage.

For the unfolding of the data, the microanalysis technique of the data was crucial for the construction of the theory. The microanalysis technique used the basic procedures of theoretical comparisons and questioning and provided a good way to sensitize the researcher and unpack the data in

the search for possible interpretations and classifications, reducing distortion or biases introduced

by the researcher (15).

Fig.3 - Code co-occurrence model (proximity of codes).

The comparisons made in microanalysis allow the researcher's prior knowledge to be applied in a reliable manner. This is because all perceptions related to a potential category and its properties remain as temporary assumptions until they are

confirmed by the data. This approach ensures an impartial and grounded assessment, where conclusions are derived from the evidence found in the collected data, thereby strengthening the validity and objectivity of the analysis (Idem).

Fig.4 - Code co-occurrence model (code overlap).

The identification of categories was carried out through conceptual reduction. This involves defining the code as a category, defining its properties, and identifying its occurrence in the data. Properties that did not find empirical support were disregarded.

After the data coding and the identification of the relationships between categories, an attempt was made to infer the central category (the story line) that could integrate all other identified categories into a main theoretical scheme. The identification of the central category arose from the prominence of one of the categories as representative of the central idea and in relation to which the other categories establish an influence - the concept of surveillance. The relationships of the subsidiary categories with the central category are made through the axial paradigm: conditions, context, strategies, and consequences - assuming that the constructed theory takes on a narrative order of the type A (conditions) leads to B (phenomenon) which occurs in C (context) which leads to D (actions) and then leads to E (consequences) (15). In summary: surveillance in post-anesthesia nursing care, when combined with the establishment of a therapeutic relationship, contributes significantly to the practice of safe care.

DISCUSSION

The prevention of clinical deterioration of the cared-for person is essentially a nursing responsibility, achieved through clinical judgment and diagnostic reasoning arising from the surveillance process (17). It is crucial to recognize that the effectiveness of nursing surveillance in preventing clinical deterioration is contingent upon various

factors, including organizational support, professional development, and a conducive work environment. According to Peet, Theobald (18), nursing surveillance weaves the tapestry of care that keeps patients safe. However, the practice of nursing surveillance is obscured by the visible outcomes of care, making it vulnerable to external systems and existing social orders. Therefore, it becomes important to reveal the hidden threads of the value of nursing knowledge, the voice of nursing, the care provided, the relationship with the cared-for person, and the value of team care. Nurses play a central role in maintaining patient safety through vigilant surveillance and proactive intervention(17, 18). However, the visibility of nursing surveillance practices may be overshadowed by the tangible outcomes of care, leaving it vulnerable to external scrutiny and the influence of existing social structures.

The Theory of Anticipatory Vigilance in perioperative nursing offers a profound framework for enhancing patient safety not only during surgery but also in the crucial post-anesthesia care phase (19). Where nursing surveillance in post-anesthesia care units is highlighted as critical and complex, the Theory of Anticipatory Vigilance also provides invaluable insights into proactive risk management and patient-centered care. By emphasizing concepts such as attention, alertness, anticipation, and watchfulness, this theory aligns perfectly with the objective of understanding the interaction between nursing surveillance and care provision to ensure patient safety (19). Through the lens of anticipatory vigilance, perioperative nurses can navigate the dynamic post-anesthesia environment with heightened awareness and responsiveness, fostering a culture of proactive risk

reduction and therapeutic engagement. These theories not only enriches our understanding of the complexities of nursing practice but also holds significant implications for enhancing the safety and quality of care in post-anesthesia settings. By integrating the principles of anticipatory vigilance into nursing surveillance practices, we can pave the way for the development of more effective interventions and theoretical models that promote safer care environments and better patient outcomes.

Preserving the therapeutic relationship allows nurses to recognize subtle signs/symptoms, investigate causality, and identify changes in the clinical state of the cared-for person. An inadequate understanding may lead nurses to (de)value the rigorous assessment of clinical data. When these are accurately assessed, clinical deterioration can be identified early, and a rapid and distinct response can be provided, offering the opportunity to reduce critical events (20). In the study by LeBlanc, Kabbe (21) about knowledge deficits concerning nursing surveillance, five themes emerged: knowledge deficits and nursing surveillance, uncertainty, workload, lack of resources, and lack of partnership/respect. In addressing the challenges posed by the current healthcare landscape, it is imperative to emphasize the importance of preserving the therapeutic relationship between nurses and their patients. This relationship serves as the cornerstone for effective surveillance, enabling nurses to discern subtle changes in patients' clinical conditions and respond promptly to mitigate adverse outcomes (20). Moreover, a deep understanding of the intricacies of the therapeutic relationship can em-

power nurses to navigate complex clinical scenarios with confidence and compassion.

The current culture of prescriptive and routine work organization results in the fragmentation of data collection, leading to inadequate and delayed decision-making (18). When nurses engage with organizational issues, such as managing an increasing workload, they normalize the process of marginalizing their own clinical knowledge and reflective practice (22). Critical reflection encourages nurses to explore the (in)adequacy of clinical practice and its impact on the team and the focus of their care. Furthermore, LeBlanc, Kabbe (21) underscore the prevalence of knowledge deficits among nurses regarding nursing surveillance, highlighting the need for ongoing education and training initiatives. In an era characterized by rapid advancements in healthcare technology and evolving clinical practices, nurses must remain abreast of the latest evidence-based guidelines and protocols to deliver optimal care. Investing in professional development opportunities can enhance nurses' diagnostic reasoning skills and equip them with the tools needed to effectively identify and address early signs of clinical deterioration. Collectively, critical reflection is a process of empowerment and professional development, becoming an important step towards sustainable and satisfying clinical practice (23). Moreover, professional valorization is a matter of safety for the person being cared for.

Therefore, it is imperative for healthcare organizations to adopt a holistic approach to workforce management, prioritizing nurse well-being and fostering a culture of collaboration and mutual respect. By promoting a culture of continuous learning, supporting reflective practice, and prioritizing

nurse empowerment and professional development, healthcare organizations can optimize the delivery of post-anesthesia nursing care and ensure positive outcomes for patients.

CONCLUSION

The study delved into the intricate realm of post-anesthesia nursing care, shedding light on its significance amidst the broader nursing practice. Through a qualitative approach grounded in Grounded Theory, the research explored the experiences of nurses providing care in Post-Anesthesia Care Units (PACUs) within a central hospital in Portugal. The findings not only uncovered the multifaceted nature of nursing surveillance in this context but also underscored its pivotal role in ensuring patient safety and preventing clinical deterioration.

Nursing surveillance emerged as a dynamic process involving the continuous collection, analysis, and interpretation of clinical data. This process, coupled with the establishment of therapeutic relationships, enables nurses to recognize subtle signs and symptoms, identify changes in patients' clinical states, and respond promptly to mitigate adverse events. However, the study revealed challenges within the practice, including knowledge deficits, workload issues, and organizational barriers, which may compromise the effectiveness of nursing surveillance.

The findings highlight the need for a shift in organizational culture towards valuing nursing knowledge and fostering reflective practice. By empowering nurses to critically reflect on their practice and advocate for patient safety, healthcare organizations can enhance the quality

of care provided in PACUs. Moreover, professional recognition and support are essential for nurses to navigate the complexities of post-anesthesia nursing care and uphold standards of excellence in patient outcomes.

In conclusion, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge in nursing by illuminating the significance of nursing surveillance in post-anesthesia care. By addressing the identified challenges and leveraging the insights gleaned from this research, healthcare professionals and organizations can work towards optimizing patient care and ensuring a safer and more supportive environment for both patients and caregivers in the post-anesthesia recovery process.

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